

“Buy to Change”: The influence of Cause-Brand Fit on Consumer Purchase Intention in Mongolian Market

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Abstract: Over the past two decades, companies have faced increasing pressure to take responsibility for the broader societal impact of their actions, extending beyond their immediate commercial interests. During this time, collaborative partnerships between businesses and nonprofit organizations have surged. Corporations are increasingly integrating cause-related marketing (CRM) into their strategies to address societal concerns and boost sales, leveraging partnerships with nonprofits. The effectiveness of CRM is debated, particularly the importance of 'fit' between the brand and the cause, with mixed findings on its impact on marketing success and consumer perception. Some studies suggest that a high fit between the brand and cause leads to positive attitudes, while others argue that fit may be irrelevant or even lead to consumer skepticism. This study aims to investigate how this alignment influences consumer purchase intentions, underlining the need to better understand the dynamics of cause-brand fit within CRM. In the study's test of hypotheses, a multiple regression analysis was employed to examine the impact of determinants on purchase intention in cause-related marketing campaigns. The results confirmed the significance of cause-brand fit, functional fit, image fit, and attitude toward CRM campaigns in influencing purchase intention. Further analysis using a bootstrapping method explored the indirect effects, revealing that attitude served as a partial mediator for functional fit and a full mediator for image fit in influencing purchase intention. The moderating role of cause affinity was assessed, showing a significant moderation effect in the relationship between image fit and customer participation behavior in cause-related marketing, but not for functional fit. Our research significantly contributes to the existing literature by deepening our understanding of how the alignment between a brand and a cause, considering both functional and image aspects, influences consumer buying intentions, with special emphasis on the role of cause affinity and highlights the importance of well-matched causes in CRM initiatives. For marketing professionals and brand managers, these findings provide valuable practical insights when planning CRM campaigns. They emphasize that CRM should be viewed as a strategy to enhance a brand's long-term value, with the alignment between the brand and the chosen cause being pivotal for authenticity and the establishment of consumer trust.

Keywords: Cause-related marketing, cause-brand fit, consumer attitude toward CRM campaign, consumer purchase intention, cause affinity.

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Introduction

In recent years, the concept of aligning brands with social causes has garnered significant interest from both scholars and industry practitioners, as evidenced by numerous studies and discussions in the field (Barone et al., 2007; Becker-Olsen et al., 2006; Lafferty, 2007; Lafferty et al., 2004; Rifon et al., 2004). Over the past two decades, collaborative partnerships between businesses and nonprofit organizations have surged. While marketing traditionally revolves around selling, influencing, and persuading consumers to buy products, companies now recognize the importance of addressing the human needs of their customers and various stakeholders, driven by both societal obligations and the desire for positive consumer responses. Consequently, a growing number of companies, regardless of size, have implemented Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs. Within the context of CSR, cause-related marketing (CRM) has garnered significant corporate attention. Cause-related marketing represents one of the fastest-growing marketing strategies today, reflecting its current relevance and the high regard marketing managers hold for this approach.

Cause-related marketing, initially defined by Varadarajan, is when a company promises to donate a specific amount to a chosen cause when customers make purchases that generate revenue, serving both organizational and individual goals. Since this initial definition, a significant amount of research has explored the various effects of CRM. The previous research has looked into how it influences consumer choices (Barone et al., 2000), purchasing decisions (Webb & Mohr, 1998), attitudes toward CRM (Barnes, 1992), and perceptions of companies engaging in such marketing efforts (Webb and Mohr, 1998). Researchers have also examined factors that can influence the impact of CRM campaigns on these factors. Notable factors include how well the cause aligns with the company (Pracejus & Olsen, 2004), the type of product involved in the CRM campaign (Strahilevitz & Myers, 1998), the context of the donation (Ellen et al., 2000) and how familiar consumers are with the cause (Lafferty & Goldsmith, 2005).

Cause-related marketing (CRM) offers numerous benefits to non-profit organizations (NPOs), businesses, and consumers. NPOs gain vital financial support, increased awareness, and reduced administrative expenses through CRM partnerships (File & Prince, 1998; Gupta & Pirsch, 2006). Businesses benefit by differentiating themselves in competitive markets, enhancing brand image, and fostering customer relationships, leading to increased sales and employee morale (Gupta & Pirsch, 2006; Mohr et al., 2001). Consumers find personal gratification in supporting a worthy cause, adding value to their purchases (Polonsky & Wood, 2001; Strahilevitz & Myers, n.d.). Companies also profit from media attention and enhanced reputation, influencing purchase intentions (Barnes & Fitzgibbons, 1991; Sana & Tarca, 2015), while consumers derive satisfaction from contributing to a noble cause, alleviating guilt and achieving personal fulfillment (Webb & Mohr, 1998; Heidarian, 2019). CRM represents a win-win-win scenario where charities, businesses, and consumers all benefit (Baker, 2003; Rajan Varadarajan & Menon, 1988a).

Cause-related marketing (CRM) campaigns are generally well-received by consumers, however, skepticism can arise when CRM campaigns mimic competitors or appear self-serving, eroding consumer trust (Drumwright, n.d.; Lee & Kim, 2016). Skepticism encompasses doubts about donation authenticity and a company's genuine commitment (Barone et al., 2000; Webb & Mohr, 1998). Such skepticism can negatively impact buying behaviors (Hammad et al., 2014). Factors like long-term campaign support, alignment with the cause, clear donation details, and generous contributions can reduce skepticism (Van Den Brink et al., 2006). Non-profit organizations also face risks, including resource allocation, donor concerns, reputation risks, and sustainability (Caesar 1986; Drumwright & Murphy 2001). Careful management is crucial to navigate these challenges effectively (Kim, 2011). To avoid such risks, marketers recommend "fit" between companies and charities to mitigate skepticism (Pracejus & Olsen, 2004).

In the context of cause-related marketing (CRM), "fit" refers to the alignment or perceived connection between a brand and the charitable cause or social issue it supports. The degree of fit can significantly influence consumer perceptions, attitudes, and purchase intentions. A strong fit often leads to more positive responses, while a weaker fit may result in skepticism or negative attitudes. In the study of how well companies and their chosen causes align in cause marketing, Gwinner (1997) was one of the first to categorize this alignment into two types: functional fit and image fit. In cause marketing, both functional and image fit are crucial but serve different roles. Functional fit is about the tangible connection between a company's offerings and the cause, while image fit involves the alignment of the brand's personality and values with the cause (Bigne et al., 2012). Understanding these aspects of fit helps companies effectively align their marketing strategies with social causes, impacting consumer perception and purchase intentions. Kim and colleagues (2012) discovered that when customers feel a high level of familiarity and activity fit with a cause, they tend to respond more positively than when the fit is low, although it doesn't change what they think about the company's reasons for supporting the cause. Lafferty and others (2004) noted that a good image fit can lead to stronger intentions to buy the product.

Purchase intention, originating from psychology and later incorporated into marketing, serves as a crucial predictor of an individual's inclination to engage in a specific buying action (Srivastava R, 2020). Defined as the likelihood that a consumer will purchase a particular product or service, brand purchase intention involves conscious planning and self-instruction, representing the anticipated final buyer response (Rossiter & Percy, 1998). In the context of cause-related marketing (CRM), purchase intention reflects a consumer's desire to support a cause through a purchase. Altruistic perceptions of CRM campaigns lead to a higher purchase intention, aligning with the consumer's sense of social consciousness (Barone et al., 2000; Boenigk & Schuchardt, 2013; Ellen, Mohr, & Webb, 2000). Scholars emphasize that purchase intention, closely tied to actual buying behavior, comprises subjective tendencies and the likelihood of making a purchase, encompassing psychological inclinations and objective probabilities (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1980).

Consumer attitudes play a pivotal role in social psychology, offering insights into general consumer behavior patterns and behaviors associated with social responsibility (Gawronski, 2007). Attitudes, defined as learned tendencies to respond positively or negatively to objects, are closely tied to reactions based on stimuli (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2004; Page and Luding, 2003). The theory of reasoned action establishes a strong link between attitudes, intentions, and actual buying behavior, suggesting that attitudes serve as reliable predictors of purchasing actions (Fishbein et al.). Cause-related marketing (CRM) emerges as a powerful tool in marketing communication, positively influencing consumer attitudes and purchase intentions (Thorne McAlister & Ferrell, 2002). The success of CRM campaigns relies on socially aware consumers engaging in pro-social behavior, supporting causes beyond self-interest (Youn & Kim, 2008). CRM proves beneficial in enhancing company image, fostering customer loyalty, and generating positive brand attitudes (Adkins, 1999; Drumwright, in Farache et al., 2008). Alignment between the brand and cause, as well as familiarity with the cause, influences consumer perceptions (Cheron et al., 2012; Zdravkovic et al., 2010). Research explores the impact of donation size and perceived company generosity, revealing that lower donation amounts may raise concerns about exploiting causes (Dahl and Lavack, 1995). Consumer support for CRM programs is evident, with a majority expressing willingness to switch brands or retailers supporting such initiatives (Cone, 1997). Over 90% of consumers consider it essential for companies to engage in responsible citizenship, particularly in sectors like the environment, education, and health (Krol, 1996). This trend underscores the growing significance of consumer expectations for socially responsible business practices.

Consumer's cause affinity" refers to how strongly a person feels connected to a social or charitable cause (Drumwright, 1996). This can range from actively supporting the cause to simply having a favorable opinion of it. When someone has low cause affinity, they're generally indifferent to the cause, which means they might not be very interested in marketing campaigns that are tied to it. However, even those with little interest in the cause might see a company's

support for it as a positive sign of its dedication to social responsibility. People with a high level of cause affinity, on the other hand, tend to have a strong emotional investment in the cause (Farache et al., 2008). They are the primary audience for cause-related marketing campaigns because they are likely to respond more enthusiastically. For these consumers, such campaigns present an additional way to support the cause they care about. People who already have a strong affinity for the cause might not be as concerned about the precise alignment between the company and the cause.

In this study, we investigate how the fit between a cause and a brand, specifically focusing on two types of fit: functional fit and image fit, can affect consumer purchase intentions. We also delve into how consumer attitudes toward CRM campaign play a role in mediating this relationship. Furthermore, we explore the moderating influence of cause affinity, as consumers often have varying levels of connection to the cause being supported.

Literature review

In recent decades, there has been a significant surge in the enthusiasm of numerous companies aiming to capture the attention of customers through cause-related marketing. Nowadays, CRM is widely regarded as a form of corporate social responsibility (CSR) efforts. Cause-related Marketing (CRM) is described as "a specific type of Corporate social initiatives" (Bae, 2016). While CRM can be seen as a component of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, as suggested by Go and Bortree (2017), it is important to recognize that CSR encompasses a broader scope, including elements like sustainability, legal and ethical practices, and notably, CRM (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

Companies face increasing pressure to actively engage in social causes and demonstrate social responsibility (Mohr et al., 2001). This has prompted the adoption of cause-related marketing (CRM) practices, which have been in use since the 1990s (Tsai, 2009). The academic literature on CRM was pioneered by Varadarajan and Menon in 1988, who not only explored the emergence of the concept but also its strategic implications. They offered the following definition: "the process of formulating and implementing marketing activities that are characterized by an offer from the firm to contribute a specified amount to a designated cause when customers engage in revenue providing exchanges and satisfy organizational and individual objectives."

As Adkins states, "Cause-Related Marketing involves utilizing marketing resources, methods, and tactics to simultaneously champion noble causes and enhance business growth" ("Cause-Related Marketing: Who Cares Wins," 1999). Another perspective defines CRM as the association between a company and a charitable organization, where the company contributes to a cause related to its products and engages consumers to boost revenue (Baker, 2003). Similarly, Cui et al., (2003) characterize CRM as a strategic partnership between businesses and non-profit causes that offer resources and funding to address social issues and business marketing goals.

As depicted in Figure 2, a CRM campaign involves three key stakeholders: the organization, non-profit organizations, and consumers, all of whom stand to benefit from such a campaign (Westberg, 2004).

Fig. 1: Three key participants in Cause-related marketing (CRM)

The term CRM was introduced by American Express in 1983 when they initiated a campaign, donating one cent for each use of the American Express charge card and one dollar for every new card issued in the U.S. for the restoration

of the Statue of Liberty. This nationwide campaign generated \$6 million, with \$1.7 million going to the Statue of Liberty Ellis Island Foundation (Wall, 1984). Significantly, American Express saw a 28% increase in card usage and a 45% rise in new cardholders during the campaign period (Wall, 1984). Since then, companies like CitiBank, Procter and Gamble, Pepsi, General Foods, Yoplait, and more recently, Domino's Pizza, have employed CRM campaigns to cultivate emotional connections with consumers (Meyer, n.d.). Over the years, there has been a notable rise in CRM campaigns, with various brands forming successful partnerships with causes, benefiting both sides (Bergkvist & Zhou, 2018). For instance, in 2008, Starbucks pledged 50 cents from every sale of their exclusive RED beverages to the Global Fund, supporting the battle against AIDS, tuberculosis, and malaria (Ferraris et al., 2020). Luxury brand Montblanc launched the "Signature for Good" initiative, directing 10% of its retail sales towards UNICEF's educational endeavors (Fazli-Salehi et al., 2019).

Although scholars do not completely agree on the definition of the concept of cause marketing, it is generally believed that cause marketing has the following characteristics: 1. It supports a well-defined charitable or social cause. 2. The business has a direct and acknowledged relationship with this chosen cause. 3. The financial support for this cause comes from the business's sales—meaning the more products or services customers buy, the more help the cause receives. Only through selling these products or services can a business raise money for the associated charity work. One of the key factors for the success of a cause-related marketing strategy is the alignment between the chosen cause and the brand, ensuring that consumers perceive a natural connection between them (Adkins 1999; DeNitto 1989; Higgins 2002; Lewis 2003). This alignment is akin to a marketing or brand alliance, and research on commercial brand alliances highlights that the fit between the partners significantly influences attitudes toward the alliance (Andreason 1996; Polonsky and Macdonald 2000; Till and Nowak 2000; Simonin and Ruth 1998). Partner selection plays a crucial role, as careful selection of the nonprofit partner, well-planned projects, and the expectation of mutual benefits are vital for success (Bucklin and Sengupta 1993; Abdy and Barclay 2001). The success of such collaborative efforts is contingent on both partners creating more value together than they could individually.

The concepts of compatibility, similarity, fit, relevance, match, and congruence are all terms that have been applied in literature to characterize how consumers perceive the relationship between a sponsor and what they choose to sponsor, whether an event or a cause (Basil & Herr, 2003). These terms all represent the same broad idea of how consumers view the connection between entities in a formalized partnership (Meenaghan, 2001). Independent of the specific type of compatibility, scholarly research has consistently demonstrated a direct correlation between the degree of perceived compatibility and the positive influence this perception has on how consumers react to the sponsorship (Trimble & Rifon, 2006). In the study of how well companies and their chosen causes align in cause marketing, Gwinner (1997) was one of the first to categorize this alignment into two types: functional fit and image fit. In cause marketing, both functional and image fit are crucial but serve different roles. Functional fit is about the tangible connection between a company's offerings and the cause, while image fit involves the alignment of the brand's personality and values with the cause (Bigne et al., 2012). Understanding these aspects of fit helps companies effectively align their marketing strategies with social causes, impacting consumer perception and purchase intentions. Kim and colleagues (2012) discovered that when customers feel a high level of familiarity and activity fit with a cause, they tend to respond more positively than when the fit is low, although it doesn't change what they think about the company's reasons for supporting the cause. Lafferty and others (2004) noted that a good image fit can lead to stronger intentions to buy the product.

Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis

When companies engage in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, including Cause-Related Marketing, it is crucial to select the right cause that aligns with their brand's values and purpose. The selection of a philanthropic cause frequently represents a pivotal element in the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives

by corporate entities, and advocating for a well-aligned cause can yield notably advantageous outcomes, particularly within the realm of cause-related marketing (Rajan Varadarajan & Menon, 1988b).

Numerous studies have investigated the impact of cause-brand fit on the outcomes of Cause-Related Marketing (CRM) campaigns (Becker-Olsen & Hill, n.d.; Lafferty et al., 2004; Pracejus & Olsen, 2004; Rifon et al., 2004; Zdravkovic et al., 2010), emphasizing the importance of establishing a congruent connection between the brand and the chosen cause. Successful organizations continually aim to bolster their brand image and select an appropriate cause for sponsorship. A strong cause-brand fit has been observed to foster a positive customer attitude towards CRM, while a poor fit can lead to customer skepticism and a negative attitude towards CRM campaigns (Bigné-Alcañiz et al., 2009; Lafferty, 2007). Research on co-branding has similarly stressed the significance of selecting a well-matched brand partner for the success of co-branding initiatives (Bucklin & Sengupta 1993, n.d.; Gupta & Pirsch, 2006; Lafferty et al., 2004). Given this context, it is pertinent to explore the influence of cause-brand fit on attitudes towards CRM.

Bigne et al. (2010) introduced a novel approach to investigating the concept of cause-brand fit, aiming to comprehensively examine its intricate aspects. This approach involved an in-depth analysis and comparison of the impact of two distinct categories of cause-brand fit, namely, functional fit and image fit, on the perception of corporate social responsibility (CSR) brands within the context of a Cause-Brand Alliances (CBA) framework. In this context, the scholarly literature has recognized two fundamental classifications of cause-brand fit, as identified by Gwinner and Eaton (1999), Lafferty et al. (2004), Rifon et al. (2004), and Trimble and Rifon (2006):

- (1) Functional fit, which determined on the comprehensive evaluation alignment between product functionalities and the characteristics and objectives of the associated social cause.
- (2) Image fit, which is determined by the presence of congruent attributes in both the brand's image or positioning and the image associated with the chosen social cause.

In line with associative learning theory, the strength of the association between a brand and a charitable cause significantly impacts a consumer's response. When consumers perceive this association more intensely, it tends to evoke a positive response, manifesting as a favorable attitude and an increased intention to engage in a purchase. The alignment between the brand and the cause plays a pivotal role in fostering the development of cognitive associations within the minds of consumers. Consequently, this cognitive synergy simplifies the perceptual and evaluative processes related to both the brand and the cause. Ultimately, this streamlined cognitive processing significantly influences consumers' intentions regarding their purchase decisions (Bigné-Alcañiz et al., 2010). In light of this background, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: The cause-brand fit (a. functional fit; b. image fit) is positively related to consumer attitudes towards CRM campaign.

Cause-Related Marketing initiatives serve as a powerful instrument within marketing communication, facilitating the attainment of specific marketing goals. According to Thorne McAlister and Ferrell (2002) and Husted and Whitehouse (2002), these initiatives are primarily aimed at fostering positive consumer attitudes, boosting purchase intentions for the associated product, and ultimately driving increased sales. The primary objective of a Cause-related marketing campaign is to drive brand sales with the ultimate purpose of generating funds for charitable contributions to the designated cause.

There is substantial evidence to indicate that consumers are inclined to wield their purchasing power as a means to reward companies whose conduct aligns with their values, especially in relation to social responsibility or a company's support for the community through cause-related marketing (Creyer, 1997; Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001; Sen & Morwitz, 1996). Schiffman and Kanuk (2004) define attitudes as a learned inclination to react favorably or unfavorably in a rational manner to a particular object. On the other hand, Page and Luding (2003) describe attitudes as psychological

predispositions that lead to rational, positive or negative responses and behaviors in response to stimuli associated with the object.

Several authors, such as Hajjat (2003), have confirmed the desired impact of cause-related marketing campaigns on consumer attitudes and their intention to purchase the associated product. Studies, as explained by Farache et al. (2008), consistently show that consumers tend to respond positively when evaluating cause-related marketing initiatives. Galan-Ladero et al. (2013) have demonstrated that attitudes toward cause-related marketing campaigns positively affect post-purchase satisfaction. Furthermore, post-purchase satisfaction with a product associated with a cause-related marketing campaign contributes positively to brand loyalty. Consequently, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2: Consumers' attitudes toward CRM campaign is positively related to their purchase intention.

Cause-related marketing initiatives, as effective marketing communication tools, can help achieve desired marketing objectives. Galan-Ladero et al. (2013) have shown that attitudes towards a cause-related marketing campaign positively affect post-purchase satisfaction. Additionally, Cheron et al. (2012) have concluded that the perceived alignment between the brand and the cause has a positive impact on consumers' perceptions of cause-related marketing. Zdravkovic et al. (2010) further emphasize that consumer attitudes are influenced not only by the congruence between the cause and the brand but also by the interaction between fit and familiarity with the cause. Schiffman and Kanuk (2004) propose a theoretical model of attitudes encompassing affective, conative, and cognitive components, with the conative aspect often serving as an indicator of consumer intent to make a purchase. Fishben et al.'s theory of reasoned action establishes a strong connection between attitudes, intentions, and buying behavior, emphasizing that attitudes are highly positively correlated with purchase intentions and can effectively predict consumer purchasing actions. Consequently, consumer behavior is directly affected by their attitudes towards specific products and associated marketing activities. Based on this literature, we propose the following hypothesis:

H3: Consumers' attitudes toward CRM campaign mediates the relationship between cause-brand fit (a. functional fit; b. image fit) and the purchase intention.

Researchers have suggested that the impact of CSR efforts on consumer responses can vary based on how much consumers support or feel connected to the chosen cause. This level of attachment to a cause has been referred to as "cause-affinity" (Drumwright, 1996) or "personal relevance" (Creyer, 1997). It has been suggested by researchers that the effect of implementing CSR on consumer responses can be contingent upon the degree of consumer support for the specific CSR cause adopted by the firm, a concept referred to as "cause-affinity" and discussed by (Drumwright, 1996). Consumer cause affinity refers to how deeply a consumer associates with a cause, either through active support or simply through personal affinity (Sen Gupta & Wadera, 2021). Issue involvement, often referred as personal relevance, is the extent to which consumers perceive social issues as having a personal significance to them (Grau & Folse, 2007). This concept clarifies how a single cause-related marketing (CRM) campaign can trigger diverse reactions among individual consumers, influenced by their personal connection to these social issues (Bigné-Alcañiz et al., 2010). In essence, issue involvement is the key factor in understanding why the same cause-related marketing efforts can have varying impacts on different consumers, depending on how much they personally relate to the underlying social issues.

In the context of corporate social initiatives, there is substantial evidence to suggest that consumers' positive attitudes and affinity toward these initiatives are closely related to their perceptions of a sponsoring corporation's social responsibility (Ross et al., 1992). Studies have shown that favorable consumer attitudes and affinity toward such initiatives can significantly enhance their willingness to purchase products associated with these initiatives (Webb & Mohr, 1998). The perception and assessment of cause-related marketing campaigns can also vary among individuals, with the choice of a cause to which people exhibit affinity being a critical factor that enhances campaign effectiveness (Arora & Henderson, 2007). Drumwright's argument (1996) emphasizes the pivotal role of people's affinity for a cause in determining the success of a communication campaign. These findings underscore the influence of affinity toward a social

cause on affective responses (Barone et al., 2007), revealing the complex interplay between consumer attitudes, social initiatives, and the choice of causes.

Building upon previous research, which highlights the influence of consumers' affinity toward social initiatives, we hypothesize that cause affinity will moderate the mediating role of consumer attitudes towards CRM campaign in the effect of cause-brand fit on consumer purchase intention.

H4: Cause affinity moderates the relationship between cause-brand fit (a. functional fit; b. image fit) and consumer attitudes towards CRM campaign.

3.1 Conceptual model

The study presents a comprehensive theoretical model that examines the mediated influence - leveraging its positive impact on consumer attitude toward CRM - of two cause-brand fit types (functional and image) on purchase intention within the context of cause-related marketing. Additionally, this framework encompasses the examination of the moderating effect of cause affinity, enhancing our ability to understand the intricate interactions among these key elements in our research.

Fig. 2: Conceptual research model

Methodology

To investigate how strategic fit influences consumer attitudes, we conducted two studies comprising pre-test and main study phases. The pre-test was conducted to identify the most suitable cause-brand fit scenario for our formal study, utilizing descriptive statistical analysis to select the optimal scenario. In the subsequent main study, we evaluated the relationship between Lacoste and the International Union for Conservation of Nature to identify fit components and assess their impact on purchase intention. Furthermore, we examined the mediating role of consumer attitudes towards cause-related marketing. PROCESS, a computational tool for path analysis-based moderation and mediation analysis developed by Andrew F. Hayes, was used to explore the moderating impact of Cause affinity.

4.1 Variable measurements

In the process of developing the measurement scale for this research, we conducted an extensive review of existing literature relevant to cause-related marketing (CRM). Subsequently, we made deliberate and considered choices in selecting appropriate scales to measure the four central variables in our study: fit type, consumer attitude towards CRM, cause affinity, and purchase intention.

In the course of choosing the measurement scale for evaluating the alignment between the cause and brand, this study carefully considered the research questions and identified two primary dimensions: functional fit and image fit. The framework for the fit type scale largely adheres to the approach outlined by Bigne (2010), who has addressed the

measurement of functional fit and image fit. In total, the functional fit (FF) and image fit (IF) scales consist of six items. These items were measured using a five-point Likert scale, with anchors (1) Strongly Disagree and (5) Strongly Agree. Attitude toward Cause-Related Marketing (A) is measured using three items based on the scale from Elham Heidarian’s 2019 study. The Likert scale points for attitude toward CRM was the same for cause-brand fit. Purchase intention (PI) was measured by four items. Each item is based on Parasuraman’s (1996) and it was measured using a five-point Likert scale, with anchors (1) Strongly Disagree and (5) Strongly Agree. The items to measure Cause affinity (CA) were adapted from Grau & Folse’s (Grau & Folse, 2007) including 5 items. The questions were measured by the 5-point Likert scale, with anchors (1) Strongly Disagree and (5) Strongly Agree.

4.2 Pretest

In the context of this research, our primary objective is to gain a comprehensive understanding of how the alignment between different types of fit in cause marketing practices exerts an influence on consumer purchase intention. In pursuit of this objective, the initial phase of our research involves the presentation of three distinct case studies about fit type activities in cause-related marketing before issuing questionnaires. Following a review of numerous cause-related marketing case studies, we identified three specific cases to use in our research. To gather data, the survey was distributed to a total of 35 individuals, with 31 of them providing responses. Respondents were asked to assess these three cases by answering questions with 6 items by Bigne’ (2010). Responses were collected using a 7-point scale, with 1 indicating “Strongly Disagree” and 7 indicating “Strongly Agree”. Descriptive statistical analysis was employed to summarize these ratings and to identify which case received the highest level of agreement from respondents. The analysis resulted in the following average scores: 34.19 for Case 1, 34.6 for Case 2, and 32 for Case 3. The highest average score was attributed to Case 2, indicating that on average, respondents rated it the most positively in terms of congruence between the company’s products and the charity cause, appropriateness, meaningfulness, correlation, and compatibility with the corporate image.

4.3 Main study

The sample collection process utilizes a combination of online and offline methods. Initially, the "snowball" sampling method is employed to distribute questionnaires among classmates, relatives, and friends. The questionnaire was administered to a diverse sample population to ensure a thorough understanding of consumer perspectives. The data collection process spanned one week, during which a total of 250 questionnaires were distributed among Mongolian consumers. Participants were required to complete all questions before submission.

The characteristics of the sample were analyzed, with the results presented in Table 5. Concerning gender distribution, 85 men, or 34% of respondents, and 165 women, or 66%, participated. In age demographics, individuals under 30 years constituted 42% of the sample. The education levels of the respondents spanned various stages. Profession-wise, corporate employees made up the most substantial segment at 29%, while retirees represented the smallest group at just 2%. In terms of income, the majority reported earnings more than MNT3,000,000 (MNT=Tugrik, the official currency of Mongolia).

4.4 Reliability and validity analysis

The initial step in evaluating the internal consistency of the research constructs involved employing Cronbach’s alpha as a reliability measure. In this study, the reliability analysis showed that Cronbach’s α values for all variables exceeded 0.85, indicating very good internal consistency. Another important factor to consider is the Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC) value, which should ideally be above 0.5 (Taan & Hajjar, 2018). The item-to-total correlation values were also above 0.69. These findings support the reliability of the questionnaire.

Variable	Question	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
Functional fit	FF1	0.772	0.871	0.895

	FF2	0.82	0.827	
	FF3	0.792	0.853	
Image fit	IF1	0.693	0.85	
	IF2	0.803	0.741	0.859
	IF3	0.718	0.818	
Attitude toward CRM	A1	0.782	0.907	
	A2	0.857	0.841	0.911
	A3	0.828	0.867	
Cause affinity	CA2	0.691	0.888	
	CA3	0.789	0.796	0.872
	CA4	0.801	0.779	
Purchase intention	PI1	0.785	0.891	
	PI2	0.811	0.882	
	PI3	0.792	0.888	0.912
	PI4	0.811	0.882	

Tab. 1: Reliability analysis

In the validity analysis, exploratory factor analysis was conducted to assess whether the operational definitions of the variables in the study were appropriate. The results indicated that all communalities exhibited patterns and distributions that were considered appropriate. This suggests that the operational definitions of the variables used in the study were valid and well-suited for the research, as they met the established criteria for factor analysis.

Result and Discussion

5.1 Test of Hypotheses

To assess Hypotheses 1, 1a, 1b, and 2, a multiple regression analysis was conducted using the SPSS macro provided by Hayes (2013). The objective was to examine the impact of various determinants on purchase intention within the context of cause-related marketing campaigns. In evaluating the significance of the determinants on purchase intention, both the p-value and t-statistics were considered. A p-value below 0.05 was set as the significance threshold, corresponding to a t-statistic exceeding 1.96 for a confidence level of 95%.

	β	Std. Error	T Statistics	P Values	R Square
Functional fit	0.154	0.058	2.68	0.008	0.7
Image fit	0.774	0.054	14.283	0.000	
Attitude toward CRM	0.621	0.057	10.991	0.000	

Tab. 2: Multiple regression analysis result

Cause-Brand Fit (H1): The effect of cause-brand fit on Attitude toward CRM campaigns was found to be significant ($\beta = 0.949, p < 0.01$), thereby confirming Hypothesis 1. Functional Fit (H1a): Functional fit demonstrated a significant positive impact on Attitude toward CRM campaigns ($\beta = 0.154, p < 0.01$), providing support for Hypothesis 1a. Image Fit (H1b): The influence of image fit on Attitude toward CRM campaigns was found to be significant ($\beta = 0.774, p < 0.01$), confirming Hypothesis 1b. Attitude toward CRM Campaign (H2): Attitude toward CRM campaigns exhibited a significant positive effect on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.621, p < 0.01$), thus supporting Hypothesis 2.

In examining the indirect effects of Cause-brand fit on Purchase Intention through the mediation of Attitude toward the Cause-Related Marketing (CRM) campaign, a bootstrapping method (PROCESS Model 4; Hayes, 2017, number of bootstrap samples = 5000) was utilized to estimate the indirect effects and their associated confidence intervals. The study investigated the mediating effect of Attitude (A) on the relationship between Functional Fit (FF) and Image Fit (IF) with Purchase Intention (PI). The analysis revealed a significant indirect effect of Functional Fit on Purchase Intention through Attitude ($\beta = 0.431, SE = 0.068, 95\% \text{ Boot CI} = [0.291, 0.558], p < 0.001$), supporting the proposed hypothesis H3a. Additionally, the indirect effect of Image Fit on Purchase Intention through Attitude was also significant ($\beta = 0.324, SE = 0.090, 95\% \text{ Boot CI} = [0.144, 0.502], p < 0.001$). On the other hand, the direct effect of Functional Fit on Purchase Intention was not significant ($\beta = 0.085, SE = 0.086, 95\% \text{ Boot CI} = [-0.084, 0.254], p = 0.323$), while the direct effect of Image Fit on Purchase Intention was significant ($\beta = 0.322, SE = 0.106, 95\% \text{ Boot CI} = [0.114, 0.521], p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that Attitude serves as a partial mediator for Functional Fit but a fully mediator for Image Fit in influencing Purchase Intention.

	β	SE	LLCI	ULCI	P
<i>Indirect effect</i>					
FF→A→PI	0.431	0.068	0.291	0.558	0.000
IF→A→PI	0.324	0.090	0.144	0.502	0.000
<i>Direct effect</i>					
FF→PI	0.085	0.086	-0.084	0.254	0.323
IF→PI	0.322	0.106	0.114	0.521	0.000
<i>Total effect</i>					
FF→PI	0.516	0.070	0.377	0.654	0.000
IF→PI	0.646	0.060	0.527	0.765	0.000

Tab. 3: Testing the mediating role of consumer attitude towards CRM

The study assessed the moderating role of Cause Affinity (CA) on the relationship between Cause-Brand Fit (CBF) and Purchase Intention (PI) using a PROCESS Model 7 (Hayes, 2017), with the number of bootstrap samples set at 5000. Hypothesis H4 suggested that Cause Affinity would moderate the indirect effect of Cause-Brand Fit on Purchase Intention through Attitude toward the CRM campaign.

For the direct relationships, functional fit (FF) to attitude (A) showed a significant effect of 0.287 ($SE = 0.062, t \text{ value} = 4.622, p < 0.001$), as did image fit (IF) to attitude (A) with an effect of 0.467 ($SE = 0.06, t \text{ value} = 7.746, p < 0.001$), and Cause Affinity (CA) to attitude (A) with an effect of 0.431 ($SE = 0.046, t \text{ value} = 9.433, p < 0.001$). The attitude (A) to purchase intention (PI) also had a significant effect of 0.384 ($SE = 0.063, t \text{ value} = 6.129, p < 0.001$).

<i>Direct relationship</i>	β	SE	T values	P
FF→A	0.287	0.062	4.622	0.000
IF→A	0.467	0.060	7.746	0.000
CA→A	0.431	0.046	9.433	0.000
A→PI	0.384	0.063	6.129	0.000
<i>Indirect relationship</i>	β	SE	T values	CI Low/High
FF→A→PI	0.150	0.038	3.958	0.081/0.232
Index of moderated mediation	0.015	0.032	0.469	-0.043/0.085
IF→A→PI	0.179	0.031	5.774	0.119/0.240

Index of moderated mediation	0.029	0.018	1.611	0.001/0.074
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Tab. 4: Testing for moderated mediation of cause affinity

Looking at the indirect relationships, the effect of functional fit (FF) through attitude (A) to purchase intention (PI) was significant at 0.150 (SE = 0.038, T value = 3.958, 95% Boot CI = [0.081,0.232]). However, the index of moderated mediation was 0.015 (SE = 0.032, t value = 0.469, 95% Boot CI = [-0.043,0.085]), indicating that the moderating role of cause affinity in this path was not statistically significant. Typically, for a moderation effect to be considered statistically significant, the confidence interval should not include zero, and the t-value should be greater than the threshold value (often 1.96 for a 95% CI). Given the t-value is less than the common threshold for significance, and the confidence interval includes zero, it does not confirm the hypothesis H4a.

Conversely, the indirect effect of image fit (IF) through attitude (A) to purchase intention (PI) was 0.179 (SE = 0.031, t value = 5.774, 95% Boot CI = [0.119,0.240]), with the index of moderated mediation being 0.029 (SE = 0.018, t value = 1.611, 95% Boot CI = [0.001,0.074]). This indicates that cause affinity does play a moderating role in the relationship between image fit and customer participation behavior in cause-related marketing, thereby confirming the H4b for this path.

5.2 Theoretical discussion

Our findings affirmatively support that functional fit between the brand and the cause would yield more favorable attitudes from consumers towards the CRM campaign. When products are promoted in cause-related marketing campaigns, consumers can easily understand their features. Even before they decide to buy, consumers can sense how well the product matches with the charitable cause it supports. If they feel the product genuinely aligns with the cause, they believe the brand is genuinely supporting a good cause based on the product's strengths. Taking part in such campaigns satisfy consumers' inherent needs for products while also fulfill the consumers' needs to supporting charity.

Secondly, our research conclusively shows that when there's a strong image alignment between the brand and the cause, consumers have a more positive view of the CRM campaign. Brands are investing heavily in shaping their image, constantly sharing their stories and updates through various platforms. As consumers get more insights about a brand's mission, strategies, and background, they develop a deeper understanding of the brand and its cause-related marketing initiatives. When they sense a strong alignment or "image fit" between the brand and the associated cause, it positively influences their decision to purchase. This bond between the brand, consumers, and the cause results in a positive response from consumers. They're not only more inclined to buy products under such campaigns but also consider them for long-term purchases.

Third, the key findings indicate that there are notable positive connections between attitudes towards CRM and the intention to make a purchase, depending on the alignment between the cause and the brand in terms of both functionality and image.

Lastly, our study makes a significant contribution to the CRM literature by emphasizing the critical role of consumers' personal relevance to a cause. While previous research (e.g., Lafferty et al. 2004, Sheik & Beise-Zee 2011, Barone et al. 2007) has highlighted the impact of cause affinity on CRM success, our findings suggest a more nuanced relationship. The differential roles of Functional and Image Fit in relation to Cause Affinity suggest that the latter may have a unique influence on consumer perception and behavior in cause-related marketing contexts. This suggests that cause affinity acts in a more complex manner, interplaying with other factors in shaping consumer attitudes. Therefore, it extends beyond acting merely as a driving force or a moderator.

Managerial implications, limitations and future research

Cause-related marketing (CRM) can be a powerful tool for marketers, but it's also sensitive and can pose risks to a company's reputation if consumers perceive it as exploiting a cause or view it with skepticism (Arora & Henderson, 2007; Basil & Herr, 2006; Murphy & Davidshofer, 1988). While the idea of businesses aligning with social causes can be

attractive to society and positively influence their perception of the company, consumers' perception of the company's motives plays a crucial role in the success of such campaigns (Barone et al., 2000). The findings of our study offer guidance to marketing professionals on planning effective CRM campaigns, particularly in terms of choosing the right charitable or social cause.

Based on our research and prior studies, it's evident that Cause-related marketing shouldn't be viewed merely as a quick sales tactic; it's a method to enhance a brand's long-term value. Both the functional and the image aspects of the brand should match with the chosen cause. This alignment guarantees that the cause marketing campaign feels authentic and resonates with the brand's core beliefs, eliminating doubts about its genuineness. A partnership that aligns well can elevate the brand's reputation, showcasing its dedication to social good, leading to greater consumer trust. For brand and marketing managers, this research highlights the importance of ensuring that the product and the cause in a cause-related marketing campaign are a good match. In simpler terms, how well the product and the cause go together can affect how people perceive the campaign. Therefore, for optimal results, it is advisable to select causes that are closely aligned with the brand's functionality or its core purpose to foster deeper emotional connection with consumers. By selecting philanthropic activities that resonate with product functions, companies signal their commitment to addressing pertinent social issues, thereby resonating with consumers who intuitively recognize these efforts. Similarly, aligning philanthropic activities with intrinsic values and external image ensures that corporate support for such causes goes beyond mere marketing strategy, effectively reflecting the company's unique characteristics and vision.

Furthermore, marketers should consider segmenting their audience based on the cause affinity levels and tailoring their messaging to leverage the moderating effect of cause affinity on the relationship between image fit and consumer behavior. For instance, campaigns that resonate with the values of consumers who have a high cause affinity are likely to be more effective in influencing their Purchase Intentions. Marketers should also note that while enhancing the functional aspects of a product is important, aligning the brand image with consumer values and the causes they care about can be even more critical, especially among consumers who already have a strong affinity for the cause.

This research exploration into cause-related marketing has several limitations that need addressing. Firstly, its failure to differentiate between various industries and products within cause-related marketing is significant. The nature and type of product can play a vital role in how consumers perceive cause marketing efforts. Secondly, while focusing on a specific demographic, like Mongolian residents, can offer localized insights, it limits the study's broader applicability. Cultural, social, or economic factors specific to Mongolia might not resonate in other global regions. Lastly, this research primarily considers the impact on consumer CRM attitudes and purchase intentions, but does not evaluate the performance of corporate brands or charitable organizations involved in cause marketing. To overcome these limitations, future research could delve into the following areas: Investigate how various product characteristics and attributes impact consumers' identification with the company and their participation in value co-creation activities. This approach would enable a more detailed examination that considers industry-specific and product-specific variables. Secondly, consider conducting a similar study on an international scale or in a different country and then compare the results with those of the current research. This comparative approach would enhance the generalizability and validity of the findings, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing consumer behavior in cause marketing across different cultural and geographical contexts. Lastly, expanding the research perspective to include the evaluation of corporate brands or charitable organizations engaged in cause marketing, using metrics like reputation indices and financial performance, would offer a more comprehensive view of the impact and effectiveness of cause marketing efforts.

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